

IN VITRO THROMBOLYTIC ACTIVITY OF ETHANOLIC EXTRACT FROM *Paspalum conjugatum* (CARABAO GRASS) AND *Eleusine indica* (PARAGIS)

Riezza Belle B. Dupale, Jasmine Mae G. Rico, Andrea Nicole A. Aquino,
Diane Jade C. Pasuquin, Cathelyn C. Mariano, LPT, MA

Bachelor of Science in Medical Laboratory Science

Abstract. Thromboembolic disorders, including ischemic heart disease and stroke, pose significant health risks, leading to urgent needs for effective treatments. As current thrombolytic agents, while effective, often have limitations such as high costs and side effects. This research aimed to assess the potential in vitro thrombolytic activity of ethanolic extracts from carabao grass (*Paspalum conjugatum*) and paragis grass (*Eleusine indica*) as a natural, cost-effective alternative for managing thromboembolic disorders. In vitro tests were used to assess the clot lysis effect of the ethanol extract from the carabao and paragis grass. Phytochemical screening revealed the presence of flavonoids and tannins in both grass extracts, indicating their potential for clot lysis. The results from thrombolytic assays showed a dose-dependent increase in clot lysis, *P. conjugatum* extract lysed the clot by 18.09 % in 2.5mg/mL, 27.59% in 5 mg/mL, 49.39% in 10 mg/mL and 65.60% in 20 mg/mL showing a steady increase with the concentration, while in *E. indica* extract it lysed 25.38 % in 2.5mg/mL, 41.53% in 5 mg/mL, 59% in 10 mg/mL and 82.67% in 20 mg/mL indicating that with the highest concentrations of both extracts achieving significant clot reduction making it the optimal concentration. . In comparison with the negative control, it showed a mere clot reduction of 0.32%. The findings suggest that carabao and paragis grass extracts possess a thrombolytic activity, warranting further investigation into their pharmacological properties and potential as natural thrombolytic agents.

Keywords: clot, lysis, flavonoids, tannins, thromboembolic disorders

I. INTRODUCTION**Background of the Study**

Currently, many individuals are impacted by thromboembolic disorders, which include a variety of conditions affecting the heart and blood vessels. The World Health Organization (WHO, 2021) identifies this category as encompassing issues such as ischemic stroke and myocardial infarction. Thrombosis is the primary cause of both ischemic heart disease and ischemic stroke. This condition occurs when blood vessels become blocked due to excessive clotting or malfunctioning anti-clotting factors, as highlighted by Ogugofor et al. (2022). If not addressed, these disorders can result in the formation of blood clots, or "thrombi," within blood vessels, leading to serious health complications.

In recent years, cardiovascular diseases (CVDs) have resulted in 17.9 million deaths, representing 32% of all fatalities, with 85% of these deaths attributed to heart attacks and strokes, making CVD a significant global health issue (WHO, 2021). The Philippine Statistics Authority reports that ischemic heart disease, also known as coronary heart disease, accounted for 105,114 deaths, or 17.14% of all fatalities (PSA, 2021). Chest pain or discomfort is a common symptom, often caused by blood clots forming in the coronary arteries. These clots contribute to the majority of CVDs by partially or completely obstructing blood vessels (Ashorobi et al., 2021).

Thromboembolic disorders, which include ischemic stroke and myocardial infarction, are significant global health challenges affecting millions of individuals. The World Health Organization (2021) identifies thrombosis as a primary cause of these conditions, leading to the formation of blood clots that obstruct blood vessels. In recent years, cardiovascular diseases (CVDs) have resulted in approximately 17.9 million deaths annually, accounting for 32% of all fatalities

worldwide. This alarming statistic underscores the pressing need for effective treatments and preventive measures to combat these life-threatening conditions. In the Philippines, ischemic heart disease, also known as coronary heart disease, was responsible for 105,114 deaths, representing 17.14% of total fatalities (Philippine Statistics Authority, 2021). Unfortunately, the lack of government support for emergency care and prevention programs hinders the effective implementation of strategies designed to combat these issues, leaving many at risk.

Current thrombolytic agents, including alteplase, streptokinase, and tissue plasminogen activator (tPA), have proven effective in dissolving blood clots but come with significant limitations. These include the need for high dosages to achieve optimal efficacy, reduced fibrin specificity, and associated risks of bleeding complications. Moreover, access to these treatments is often limited, particularly in low- and middle-income countries like the Philippines, where they can be costly and frequently unavailable. This situation has spurred ongoing research initiatives aimed at developing new thrombolytic medications that focus on improving site specificity and minimizing side effects. This study aims to examine the thrombolytic properties of various grasses in human blood. The selected grass samples were also tested for their antibacterial activity, as many diseases prevalent in local communities are frequently associated with bacterial infections. However, no research has been conducted on their thrombolytic potential.

Carabao grass is traditionally utilized for its health benefits, including treatment for wounds and various ailments. Its bioactive compounds, such as flavonoids and tannins, are believed to contribute to its therapeutic properties. Similarly, *paragis* is known for its antibacterial, antiviral, and anti-inflammatory effects, making it a valuable resource in traditional medicine. Preliminary research has indicated that both plants may possess significant thrombolytic activity, positioning them as potential cost-effective alternatives to current thrombolytic therapies.

The findings of this study not only emphasize the potential of carabao grass and paragis as natural thrombolytic agents but also align with Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs). Specifically, this research supports SDG 3, which aims to ensure good health and well-being for all individuals, and SDG 9, which encourages innovation and sustainable industrial practices. By highlighting the efficacy of these herbal extracts, the study opens avenues for further exploration of their bioactive compounds, fostering innovation in the development of safer and more accessible treatments for thromboembolic disorders, and ultimately addressing health disparities in underserved communities.

Statement of the Objectives

This study aimed to determine the *in vitro* thrombolytic activity of ethanolic extract from carabao grass (*P. conjugatum*) and paragis grass (*E. indica*). It was conducted from January to March 2025.

Specifically, it sought to:

1. Determine the secondary metabolites of the ethanolic extract from carabao grass *and* paragis grass using the test tube method.
2. Determine the percentage of clot reduction before and after treatment in the following concentrations:
 - a. 2.5 mg/mL carabao grass extract;
 - b. 5 mg/mL carabao grass extract;
 - c. 10 mg/mL carabao grass extract;
 - d. 20 mg/mL carabao grass extract.

3. Determine the percentage of clot reduction before and after treatment in the following concentrations:
 - a. 2.5 mg/mL paragis grass extract;
 - b. 5 mg/mL paragis grass extract;
 - c. 10 mg/mL paragis grass extract;
 - d. 20 mg/mL paragis grass extract.

II. METHODOLOGY

Research Design

An experimental in vitro design was used to evaluate the thrombolytic activity of ethanol extracts from *carabao* and *paragis* grass. Procedures included blood collection, crude extraction, and testing various concentrations for clot lysis effects.

Study Site and Sample Collection

Carabao grass was collected from Purok 2, Baresbes, Quezon, Nueva Vizcaya, a location near a river and distant from pollution sources such as vehicle emissions. Paragis grass was gathered in Salvacion, Saguday, Quirino, where it was found to be abundant and ideal for sampling. All laboratory procedures, including extraction and testing, were conducted at the SMU–Center for Natural Sciences Research Laboratory.

Specimen Identification

The collected sample of *Paspalum conjugatum* (carabao grass) and *Eleusine indica* (paragis) was submitted to the Dean of the College of Forestry, Environment and Resource Management of Nueva Vizcaya State University, Bayombong, Nueva Vizcaya for its taxonomic identity. The experts carefully analyzed it to ensure that the plant samples are correctly positioned within established categories to bolster its reliability.

Blood Donors

The study involved one male volunteer donor who provided 12 mL of blood through venipuncture using a non-additive evacuated tube system, monitored by a Registered Medical Technologist (RMT). The donor met WHO screening criteria, including being at least 18 years old, weighing 45 kg or more, not on anticoagulants, and free from recent tattoos or blood-related illnesses. A health screening questionnaire was used to ensure donor suitability, and informed consent was obtained, with all data kept confidential.

Data Gathering Procedure

Preparation of Carabao and Paragis Grass

The collected leaves of carabao and paragis grass were thoroughly washed to eliminate dirt and contaminants. After cleaning, the leaves were air-dried to remove moisture and prepare them for extraction.

Crude Extraction

The leaves were air-dried for two to three days, then oven-dried at 55°C until crispy and brown. The dried leaves were ground into a fine powder using a laboratory blender. Five hundred

grams of the powder were soaked in 1000 mL of ethanol for 48 hours, then filtered through cheesecloth. The filtrate was concentrated using a rotary evaporator under vacuum.

Test Tube Phytochemical Test

Following Ghaeni et al. (2022), flavonoids were detected by mixing 0.5 mL of the extract with sodium hydroxide (NaOH) and then hydrochloric acid (HCl), a color change from yellow to colorless indicated flavonoid presence. For tannins, the extract was combined with diluted ferric chloride, where a blue-black color indicated gallic tannins, and green to blue-green signified catechin tannins.

Thrombolytic Concentration Formulation

The carabao and paragis grass extracts were each mixed with normal saline solution to prepare thrombolytic formulations at four concentrations: 2.5 mg/mL, 5 mg/mL, 10 mg/mL, and 20 mg/mL, with each concentration placed in separate test tubes for testing.

Blood Collection and Processing

Blood was collected under RMT supervision using 24 sterile, pre-weighed, non-additive evacuated tubes, each containing 500 μ L of blood from a healthy donor. The tubes were kept upright and undisturbed during processing.

Thrombolytic Assay

The blood samples were incubated at 37°C for 60 minutes to form clots, then centrifuged for 5 minutes to separate clots from serum. The clot weight was measured after serum removal. Each clot was treated with different concentrations (2.5, 5, 10, and 20 mg/mL) of carabao and paragis grass extracts and incubated for 90 minutes to assess clot lysis.

Percentage of Clot Reduction

The clot weight before and after treatment was recorded to determine thrombolytic activity. The percentage of clot reduction was calculated using the formula:

$$\% \text{ Clot reduction} = \frac{\text{Clot (g) before treatment} - \text{Clot (g) after treatment}}{\text{Clot (g) before treatment}} \times 100$$

This value reflects the effectiveness of the carabao and paragis grass extracts in lysing the clot.

Selection of the Optimum Concentration

The optimum concentration was determined by comparing the percentage of clot reduction across all tested concentrations. The concentration that showed the highest clot reduction was selected as the most effective. Statistical analysis was used to validate the results and ensure consistency.

Treatment of Data

The thrombolytic activity of the different concentrations was measured using the % Clot reduction method. The mean of the results obtained was computed for the selection of the optimal concentration.

Ethical Consideration

The study received ethical approval from the Saint Mary's University Research Ethics Board (SMUREB), located at 2nd Floor, Rev. John Van Bauwel Hall, SMU Main Campus, Bayombong, Nueva Vizcaya, Philippines. Contact details are email: reb@smu.edu.ph and cellphone: 09177053041.

Laboratory Safety

All laboratory procedures were scheduled and supervised by the laboratory assistant at the Center for Natural Sciences. Protective gear, including gowns, gloves, and masks, was worn throughout the activities. The assistant provided guidance on using equipment such as the blender, centrifuge, cheesecloth, rotary evaporator, analytical balance, and airtight containers. Blood collection was supervised by a Registered Medical Technologist.

Waste Disposal

Residual pulverized carabao grass was discarded into a biodegradable pit. Sharp materials were placed in puncture-proof containers and autoclaved. Non-anticoagulant tubes were disposed of in a hazardous waste container.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Section 1: Phytochemical Screening of Carabao grass and Paragis grass

Figure 4

Presence of Tannins and Flavonoids in Carabao Grass

Carabao grass

Legend: Blue color – presence of tannins

Yellow to colorless – presence of flavonoids

Paragis grass

Legend: Blue color – presence of tannins

Yellow to colorless – presence of flavonoids

The figure above shows the presence of flavonoids and tannins in carabao grass and paragis with the use of the tube method. Still, since the result in the test tube method was not that visible, the spot test was used as the confirmation. Point five (0.5) mL of the carabao grass extract and paragis grass extract is mixed with sodium hydroxide (NaOH), followed by the addition of hydrochloric acid (HCl), resulting in a yellow to colorless color that indicates the presence of flavonoids. With the use of diluted ferric chloride that is mixed with the carabao grass extract and paragis grass extract resulted in a blue color that indicates positive in tannins.

According to Garduque et al. (2019), carabao grass phytochemical constituents are highly abundant in flavonoids, triterpenes, saponins, glycosides, tannins, and traces of alkaloids. Afrose et al. (2024) stated that the ethanolic extract of *Paspalum conjugatum* contains alkaloids, tannins, flavonoids, and glycosides. Adoho et al. (2021) examine the diverse secondary metabolite profile of *E. indica*, which includes alkaloids, terpenes, flavonoids, tannins, anthraquinones, saponins, cardiac glycosides, and anthracene glycosides.

Therefore, carabao grass and paragis grass show a positive result in flavonoids with a yellow to colorless color and in tannins with a blue color. The secondary metabolites are responsible for the blood clot lysis.

Section 2. Thrombolytic Activity of *Paspalum conjugatum*

Table 1

Thrombolytic Activity of Ethanolic Extract of Paspalum conjugatum

Concentrations	Mean of Weight (g) Before	Mean of Weight (g) After	Mean of Percentage Clot Reduction (%)
20 mg/mL	.259	.089	65.60
10 mg/mL	.301	.152	49.39
5 mg/mL	.402	.291	27.59
2.5 mg/mL	.269	.220	18.09

The table above shows the thrombolytic effect of the ethanolic extract of carabao grass at various concentrations. The results indicate a dose-dependent effect: as the concentration increases, the percentage of clot lysis also rises. Specifically, at 2.5 mg/mL, clot lysis is 18.09%, which increases to around 27.59% at 5 mg/mL, 49.39% at 10 mg/mL, with a steady increase that peaks at 65.60% at the highest concentration (20 mg/mL).

This finding aligns with the study by Culliao et al. (2020), which demonstrated that the highest concentration of the extract from *Termitomyces eurhizus* achieved the highest clot reduction percentages, measuring $35.19 \pm 0.13\%$ and $32.41 \pm 0.17\%$. Additionally, Akbor et al. (2023) reported a concentration-dependent clot lysis effect in the methanolic leaf extract of *Celtis tenuifolia*, with maximum clot lysis observed at the highest concentration, measuring 198.41 ± 1.87 μg . In comparison, the positive control, streptokinase, used in the study of Afalla et al. (2024) revealed a clot reduction percentage of 89.70%, whereas the negative control showed a mere clot reduction of 0.32%.

Thus, the highest concentration (20 mg/mL) of carabao grass exhibits the greatest thrombolytic activity among all tested concentrations, establishing it as the optimal concentration. This suggests that ethanolic extract effectively enhances clot lysis.

Section 3. Thrombolytic Activity of *Eleusine indica*

Table 2

Thrombolytic Activity of Ethanolic Extract of Eleusine indica

Concentrations	Mean of Weight (g)		Mean of Percentage Clot Reduction (%)
	Before	After	
20 mg/mL	.394	.068	82.67
10 mg/mL	.355	.145	59.00
5 mg/mL	.370	.216	41.53
2.5 mg/mL	.373	.278	25.38

Based on the above table, the thrombolytic effect of *Eleusine indica* ethanolic extract increases in a dose-dependent manner. The extract shows a 25.38% clot reduction at the lowest concentration (2.5 mg/mL). It rises steadily with each higher dose until it reaches 82.67% at 20 mg/mL.

This aligns with the findings of Rahaman et al. (2020), where their results demonstrated that increased concentrations of *Rudbeckia hirta* leaf extract led to better clot lysis. The study of Culliao et al. (2020) also proved that the greatest concentration of chloroform and ethanol extracts of *Termitomyces eurrhizus* likewise had the largest clot reduction percentages, measuring $35.19 \pm 0.13\%$ and $32.41 \pm 0.17\%$, respectively. In comparison, the positive control, streptokinase, used in the study of Afalla et al. (2024) showed a clot reduction percentage of 89.70%, while the negative control exhibited a clot reduction of only 0.32%.

The 20 mg/mL concentration of *E. indica* exhibits the highest thrombolytic activity among all tested concentrations, making it the optimal concentration. Therefore, this suggests that the plant extract possessed significant thrombolytic activity.

The ethanolic extract of *Eleusine indica* demonstrates a clear dose-dependent thrombolytic effect. At the lowest concentration of 2.5 mg/mL, the extract achieves a 25.38% reduction in clot size, which steadily increases to 82.67% at the highest concentration of 20 mg/mL. This finding aligns with research by Rahaman et al. (2020), which showed that higher concentrations of *Rudbeckia hirta* leaf extract resulted in improved clot lysis. Similarly, Culliao et al. (2020) reported significant clot reductions with increased concentrations of chloroform and ethanol extracts from *Termitomyces eurrhizus*.

IV. CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Conclusions

This study aimed to determine the in vitro thrombolytic activity of ethanolic extracts from carabao grass (*Paspalum conjugatum*) and paragis grass (*Eleusine indica*). Phytochemical tests conducted in a spot test revealed the presence of flavonoids and tannins in both plants, indicating that the plant extracts are good sources for clot lysis. This ethanolic extract of *Paspalum conjugatum* demonstrated the ability to lyse clots even at the lowest concentration, with the highest thrombolytic activity occurring at the highest concentration tested. Similarly, the ethanolic extract of *Eleusine indica* showed the highest percentage of thrombolytic activity at its highest concentration while still retaining clot lysis capability at lower concentrations. Thus, both plants could serve as potential sources of natural thrombolytic agents, as their activity demonstrates a significant ability to lyse blood clots. This study represents only a preliminary investigation of their thrombolytic activity; further research into their pharmacological and medicinal properties is essential to fully explore their potential as thrombolytic agents fully.

Recommendations

1. Utilizing their pharmaceutical development, given their demonstrated safety (non-toxic) and efficacy, these grass extracts could be further investigated for incorporation into pharmaceutical formulations. This could lead to the development of herbal medicines or supplements aimed at improving cardiovascular health.
2. Move from in vitro to in vivo studies to evaluate the thrombolytic activity of these extracts in animal models. This is crucial for assessing their safety and efficacy.
3. If in vivo studies yield positive results, consider planning pre-clinical trials to evaluate the efficacy and safety of the extracts in humans.
4. Collaborate with pharmacologists and medicinal chemists to enhance understanding of the extracts' properties and to facilitate the development of new thrombolytic agents.

References

- Abbas, A., Naqvi, S. A. R., Rasool, M. H., Noureen, A., Mubarik, M. S., & Tareen, R. B. (2021). Phytochemical analysis, antioxidant, and antimicrobial screening of *Seriphidium oliverianum* plant extracts. *Dose-Response*, 19(1), 155932582110047. <https://doi.org/10.1177/15593258211004739>
- Adoho, A. C. C., Zinsou, F. T., Olounlade, P. A., Azando, E. V. B., Hounzangbe-Adote, M. S., & Gbangboche, A. B. (2021). Review of the literature on *Eleusine indica*: phytochemical, toxicity, pharmacological, and zootechnical studies. *Journal of Pharmacognosy and Phytochemistry*, 10(3), 29–33. <https://doi.org/10.22271/phyto.2021.v10.i3a.14060>
- Afalla, B. J. E., Bagcal, G. G. D., Sebbey, C. J., & Yanos, J. M. G. (2024). *Thrombolytic activity of flavonoids from arugula (Eruca sativa) crude extract* [Research Paper]. Saint Mary's University.
- Akah, P.A. and Ezeugo, A.O. (2020). *Eleusine indica* Linn, Baertin (Poaceae) Ethanol leaf extract and its ethyl acetate fraction display potential anti-inflammatory activities. *Journal of Pharmaceutical Research International*, [online] pp.75–86. doi:<https://doi.org/10.9734/jpri/2020/v32i1330587>.
- Akbor, Md. S., Al Hasan, Md. S., Haque, Mst. F., Hossain, Md. S., Tanim, T. I., Sheikh, S., Faruq, A. A., & Islam, M. T. (2023). Clot lysis and membrane protection potentials of *Cheilanthes tenuifolia* methanolic leaf extract. *Khulna University Studies*, 122–130. <https://doi.org/10.53808/kus.2023.20.02.1019-ls>
- Ali, M. R., Salim Hossain, M., Islam, M. A., Saiful Islam Arman, M., Sarwar Raju, G., Dasgupta, P., & Noshin, T. F. (2014). Aspect of thrombolytic therapy: A review. *The Scientific World Journal*, 2014(1), 586510. <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/books/NBK557411/>
- Aqueous and Ethanolic Extracts of the Selected Species of Medicinal Plants. *Proceedings*, 41(1), 47. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ecsoc-23-06703>
- Ashorobi, D., Ameer, M., & Fernandez, R. (2022). Thrombosis. <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/books/NBK538430/>
- Baig, M. U., & Bodle, J. (2023). *Thrombolytic Therapy*. National Library of Medicine; StatPearls Publishing. <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/books/NBK557411/>

- Bantiling, K., Galanido, L., and Tubog, D. (2023). Antibacterial activity of Carabao grass (*Paspalum conjugatum*) Extract Against *Staphylococcus epidermidis* and *Escherichia coli*. <https://ejournals.ph/article.php?id=23484>
- Baoru, Y. & Pengzhan, L. (2013). Composition and biological activities of hydrolyzable tannins of the fruits of *Phyllanthus emblica*. *Journal of Agricultural and Food Chemistry*, 62(3), 529-541.
- Calago, P. M., Dayao, M. R., Kent, R. P., Saquilabon, Cyrille Rosbelle, Tecson, J. M., Anne, J., & Arong, E. (2015). The effect of cogon grass (*Imperata cylindrica*) and carabao grass (*Paspalum conjugatum*) leaf extract on the mortality of *Aedes aegypti* larvae. *Herdin.ph*. <https://www.herdin.ph/index.php?view=research&cid=60816>
- Capiral, M. G., Adorna, M. T., Capistrano, I. T., Ann, R., Caranto, A., Marie, D., ... & Torres, R. G. Thrombolytic effect of water lettuce (*Pistia stratiotes*) leaves ethanol extract: an in vitro study.
- Chang, Hui, et al. "An Overview of Fructus Meliae Toosendan: Botany, Traditional Uses, Phytochemistry, Pharmacology and Toxicology." *Biomedicine & Pharmacotherapy*, vol. 157, Jan. 2023, p. 113795, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biopha.2022.113795>. Accessed 18 Jan. 2023
- Collantes, M. E., Navarro, J., Belen, A., & Gan, R. (2022). Stroke systems of care in the Philippines: Addressing gaps and developing strategies. *Frontiers in Neurology*, 13, 1046351.
- Culliao, A. G. L., Lumang-ay, R. S., Kingat, G. M. T., Colallad, T. P., & Canaria, M. V. P. (2020). Preliminary bioactivity screening of crude extracts of six wild macrofungi from pine forests in Benguet and Mt. Province, Philippines. *Manila Journal of Science*. <https://www.dlsu.edu.ph/wpcontent/uploads/pdf/research/journals/mjs/MJS13-2020/volume-1/MJS13-6-2020-culliao-et-al.pdf>
- Datorin, X.T., Jonathan D Liboon, Barazan, P.N. and Guanzon, L.A. (2020). *Anti-angiogenic activity of carabao grass (Paspalum conjugatum) extracts in cam assay*. [online] Available at: https://www.researchgate.net/publication/363467735_Anti-Angiogenic_Activity_of_Carabao_Grass_Paspalum_conjugatum_extracts_in_cam_assay.
- Elshafie, H. S., Ippolito Natale Camele, & Mohamed, A. A. (2023). A comprehensive review of the biological, agricultural, and pharmaceutical properties of secondary metabolites based on plant origin. *International Journal of Molecular Sciences*, 24(4), 3266–3266. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijms24043266>
- Esparagoza, C., & Gallego, R. (2020). (PDF) Antimicrobial, characterization, phytochemical analysis, and cytotoxicity level of chloroform, acetone, and hexane leaf extracts of *Paspalum conjugatum* (Sour Paspalum). *Www.researchgate.net*. https://www.researchgate.net/publication/341314279_AntimicrobialCharacterization_Phytochemical_Analysis_and_Cytotoxicity_Level_of_ChloroformAcetone_and_Hexane_leaf_extracts_of_Paspalum_conjugatum_Sour_Paspalum
- Ettebong, E., & Obot, D. (2020). A Systematic review on *Eleusine indica* (L.) Gaertn.): From ethnomedicinal uses to pharmacological activities Ette O Ettebong, Peace ME Ubulom and Daniel Obot. ~ 262 ~ *Journal of Medicinal Plants Studies*, 8(4), 262–274. <https://www.plantsjournal.com/archives/2020/vol8issue4/PartD/8-4-19-640.pdf>

- Garduque, D. A. P., et al. (2019, December 18). Antimicrobial efficacy of carabao grass leaves on *Staphylococcus aureus*. *Abstract Proceedings International Scholars Conference*, 7(1), 384–397. <https://doi.org/10.35974/isc.v7i1.1035>
- Gawat, M., & Martinez, D. T. (2019). Heavy metal and health risk assessment of paragis (*Eleusine indica*) grass concoction from different parts of Laguna near the Laguna Lake Shore Line. *Journal of Human Ecology*, 8(1). <https://ovcre.uplb.edu.ph/journalsuplb/index.php/JHE/article/download/419/356>
- Ghaeni, M., Shamsi, M., & Khodadadi, 1. (2022). Phytochemical screening and evaluation of analgesic activity of *Oroxylum indicum*. *Malaysian Journal of Analytical Sciences*, 20(5), 1181-1190. <https://doi.org/10.17576/mjas-2020-2005/25>
- Gregory, H., Robin R., & Steven, S. (2017). Flavones: Food sources, bioavailability, metabolism, and bioactivity. 8(3). *Advances in Nutrition*, 423-435.
- Gruyal, G. (2014). Ethnomedicinal plants used by residents in Northern Surigao del Sur, Philippines. *Natural Products Chemistry & Research*, 2(4). <https://doi.org/10.4172/2329-6836.1000140>
- Guguloth, S. K., Malothu, N., Kadiri, S. K., & Kunuru, S. (2022). Thrombolytic property of herbal plants: A short review. *Biomedical and Pharmacology Journal*, 15(2), 837–846. <https://biomedpharmajournal.org/vol15no2/thrombolytic-property-of-herbal-plants-a-short-review/>
- Husain, F., Islam, A., Bulbul, L., Moghal, M., and Hossain, M. (2014). In vitro thrombolytic potential of root extracts of four medicinal plants available in Bangladesh. <https://doi.org/10.4103%2F0257-7941.144620>
- Islam, S., Koly, S., Zaman, S., Sukorno, F., Ahammed, S., Munira, S., & Hridoy, R. (2018). Estimation of phytochemical, antioxidant screening profile, and thrombolytic activities of methanolic extract of *Antidesma bunius* L. leaf. *Int. J. Hort. Sci. Technol*, 6, 358-363.
- Jorge, T.S. et al. . (2017). Natural biflavonoids modulate macrophage-oxidized LD interaction in vitro and promote atheroprotection in vivo. *Frontiers in Immunology*, 923.
- Jr Stuart, G. (2015, September). Laua-laua. *Philippine Medicinal Plant*.
- Jyothi, G Reddy, et al. (2020). Antidiabetic and antidyslipidemic activities of ethanol fractions of *Paspalum conjugatum* in high-fat diet and streptozotocin-induced diabetic rats. *Pharmacognosy Research*, 2020. <https://doi.org/10.4103/pr.pr.6.20>.
- Kashyap, P., Shikha, D., Gautam, S., & Rani, U. (2023). *Eleusine Indica*. In *Harvesting Food from Weeds* (pp. 113–141). <https://doi.org/10.1002/9781119793007.ch4>
- Laryea, M.K. and Borquaye, L.S. (2019). antimalarial efficacy and toxicological assessment of extracts of some Ghanaian medicinal plants. *Journal of Parasitology Research*, [online] 2019, p.e1630405. Doi:<https://doi.org/10.1155/2019/1630405>.
- Lukose, J., N, M., Mohan, G., Shastry, S. and Chidangil, S. (2019). Normal saline-induced deoxygenation of red blood cells probed by optical tweezers combined with the micro-Raman technique. *RSC Advances*, [online] 9(14), pp.7878–7884. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1039/C8RA10061F>.

- Makinano, D., & Cimafranca, L. (2020). Utilization of unwanted weed, paragis leaves (*Eleusine indica* Linn.) in cookie production. *Central Mindanao University Journal of Science*, 24(1). <https://doi.org/10.52751/eznswc95>
- Ogugofor, M. O., Njoku, U. O., Njoku, O. U., & Batiha, G. E. S. (2022). Phytochemical analysis and thrombolytic profiling of *Costus afer* stem fractions. *Future Journal of Pharmaceutical Sciences*, 8, 1-5.
- Panche, A. N., Diwan, A. D., & Chandra, S. R. (2016). Flavonoids: An overview. *Journal of Nutritional Science*, 5, e47. doi:10.1017/jns.2016.41
- Philippine Statistics Authority. *Updated Projected Population Based on 2015 OPCEN*. Available online at: <https://psa.gov.ph/content/updated-population-projections-based-results-2015-popcen>
- Philippine Statistics Authority (2021). *Registered Deaths in the Philippines, 2021 | Philippine Statistics Authority | Republic of the Philippines*. [online] psa.gov.ph. <https://psa.gov.ph/content/registered-deaths-philippines-2021>.
- Pizzi, A. (2021). Tannins' medical/pharmacological and related applications: A critical review. *Sustainable Chemistry and Pharmacy*, 22, 100481.
- Rahaman, M. Z. (2020). Assessment of thrombolytic, antioxidant, and analgesic properties of a medicinal plant of the Asteraceae family growing in Bangladesh. *Discovery Phytomedicine - Journal of Natural Products Research and Ethnopharmacology*, 7(1), 47. <https://doi.org/10.15562/phytomedicine.2020.118>
- Rashid, M. H. O., Akter, M., Uddin, J., Islam, S., Rahman, M., Jahan, K., ... & Sadik, G. (2023). Antioxidant, cytotoxic, antibacterial, and thrombolytic activities of *Centella asiatica* L.: possible role of phenolics and flavonoids. *Clinical Phytoscience*, 9(1), 1-9. <https://clinphytoscience.springeropen.com/articles/10.1186/s40816-023-00353-8#ref-CR12>
- Sayeed, M. A., Kabir, H., Rashid, M. M., Bhuiyan, M. F., & Rashid, M. A. (2015). Thrombolytic activity of methanolic extracts of *Desmodium paniculatum* (L.) and *Sarcochlamys pulcherrima* (Roxb.). *Bangladesh Pharmaceutical Journal*, 17(1), 67-69. <https://doi.org/10.3329/bpj.22318>
- Sieniawska, E., and T. Baj. "Tannins." *Pharmacognosy*, 2017, pp. 199-232, www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/B978012802104000010X, <https://doi.org/10.1016/b978-0-12-802104-0.00010-x>.
- Songco, C., Cai, W., Lanugan, S. K., Misador, C., Rondobio, K. R. B., Saarenas, K., ... & Zerda, B. J. (2023). In vitro thrombolytic activity of the ethanolic fruit pulp extract of *Crescentia cujete* (calabash) on human whole blood. *Journal of Scientific Investigations*, 2(1), 27-34. <http://jsi.cebudoctorsuniversity.edu/index.php/jsi/article/view/50>
- Sukor, S., Zahari, Z., Rahim, N., Yusoff, J., & Salim, F. (2022). Chemical constituents and anti-proliferative activity of *Eleusine indica* (L.) Gaertn. *Sains Malaysiana*, 51(3), 873-882. <https://doi.org/10.17576/jsm-2022-5103-21>

- World Health Organization. (2021, June 11). Cardiovascular Diseases (CVDs). *World Health Organization*. [https://www.who.int/news-room/fact-sheets/detail/cardiovascular-diseases-\(cvds\)](https://www.who.int/news-room/fact-sheets/detail/cardiovascular-diseases-(cvds))
- Yaacob, W. A., Ibrahim, N., & Tahir, M. M. (2014). Cytotoxicity and antiviral activities of *Asplenium nidus*, *Phaleria macrocarpa*, and *Eleusine indica*. <https://doi.org/10.1063/1.4895259>
- Zhu, Li. (Nov. 2018). Tannic Acid Inhibits Protein Disulfide Isomerase, Platelet Activation, and Thrombus Formation. *Blood*, 132(1) 29, 2418–2418, <https://doi.org/10.1182/blood-2018-99-114418>